

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP8 – Scientific coordination, project management & sustainability

D8.16 Minutes of annual general assembly meeting 3

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Abstract

The 3rd virtual General Assembly meeting was held on 6 & 7 April 2022 providing the consortium with the chance for highlighting the key achievements from year 3 of the project. During the GAM ConcePTION's high-level communication and sustainability activities and plans were also presented.

It was a great opportunity for all the members to catch up with the work that other WPs are undertaking and to show their achievements; and to address our overarching vision 'to radically and rapidly reduce uncertainty about the effects of medication used during pregnancy and breastfeeding'.

Despite the limitations due to the COVID-19 pandemic, leaders of work packages and members of ConcePTION attended the meeting and participated in the presentations. The members of the Advisory Board of ConcePTION also attended the GAM meeting and provided their feedback. The feedback provided by the members of the Advisory Board will be used for the deliverable D8.11 - Report from Advisory Board and Ethic Report. The IMI Project Officer of ConcePTION was also present during the meeting and gave a presentation to the consortium regarding the importance of ConcePTION for IMI and provided general feedback.

Planning and Outcome

The PMO was involved in the coordination and organisation of the virtual General Assembly meeting (GAM) which was held on a popular video web-conferencing and webinar platform (Zoom). The various agendas for the virtual GAM were laid-out and circulated in advance. All the partners, stakeholders and colleagues actively involved in ConcePTION were invited to this virtual General Assembly. Over 120 consortium members joined the virtual GAM and on both the days, the Project Coordinator and the Project Lead welcomed all the participants and laid out the structure for the meeting. The following was presented and discussed during the first day of the GAM:

Day 1 Agenda – ConcePTION GAM (April 6, 15:00-17:00 CET)

Agenda Wednesday, April 6	Time (CET)
Welcome and introduction	15:00 – 15:05 (5 min)
Achievements in ConcePTION during year 3	15:05 – 15:20 (15 min)
WP8 - The sustainability of ConcePTION	15:20 – 15:45 (25 min)
Presentations on key topics (10 min + 5 min Q&A for each WP) WP1: Challenges with generating a single reference list of teratogens by Sue Jordan WP2: WP2 CDE & CDM for primary data collection WP5: Overview of key challenges for sustainability of Knowledge Bank	15:45 – 16:30 (45 min)
WP8 - Communication activities of ConcePTION	16:30 – 16:40 (10 min)
Q&A + Closing	16:40 – 17:00 (20 min)

innovative
medicines
initiative

Figure 1: Agenda for day 1 of the GAM.

GAM - Day 1

ConcePTION Achievements of year 3

The aim of this presentation was to share the core achievements of ConcePTION in year 3. For this, every work package leader sent major achievements from their respective work package, which were presented by the Management Team. The major achievements are listed here (see Figures 2 and 3).

Year 3 achievements of 'core content' WPs

Figure 2: ConcePTION achievements of Year 3

Year 3 achievements of supporting WPs

Figure 3: ConcePTION Year 3 achievements of supporting WPs

The sustainability of ConcePTION

This presentation covered the progress of sustainability, why it is important to act now, where we are today, as well as the next steps for the other WPs. It also included a roadmap to sustainability building of WP6 deliverables, as well as a sequence of engagement with funders or key stakeholders. Furthermore, the organisation of sustainability into clusters within a learning ecosystem was presented. A sustainability dashboard structured in three steps was introduced. This was followed by the consortium's approach to reach their end goal: ConcePTION Lean Canvas as summary and central element in the 3-year business plan.

Presentation on key topics:

The leaders from every work package had the opportunity to present the most relevant topic or study from year 3. The following topics from every work package were presented:

Work Package 1 – *Challenges with generating a single reference list of teratogen*

WP1 provided an overview of how the consortium is going to address the potential confounders and covariates when looking at perinatal outcomes. Initially, the reasons and challenges for creating a single list of covariates and confounders were explained. Then the potential confounders on the list were described. The list of medical conditions that could serve as potential confounders together with that of medicines known to be teratogens was also reported. Lastly, an approach to handle potential confounders was suggested.

Work package 2 – *Improving the collection, analysis, and interpretation of primary pregnancy pharmacovigilance data*

WP2 started out with a description of its challenge in the current situation and the respective consequences. This was followed by an explanation of how WP2 will radically and rapidly reduce uncertainty about the effects of medications during pregnancy and breastfeeding. A Common Data Model approach by converting diverse primary source data to WP2 Core Data Elements and Definitions was reported. WP2 also presented the next steps towards integrating its primary data collection in EU-wide pregnancy. It concluded with an overview of how to make their strategy sustainable.

Work Package 5 – *Overview of key challenges for sustainability of Knowledge Bank*

The presentation of WP5 explained the following key challenges facing the Knowledge Bank sustainability: organisation, trustworthiness and visibility, up to date information, and accessibility.

Work Package 8 – *Communication activities in ConcePTION during year 3*

At the beginning WP6 provided an overview of the audiences, objectives, and tactics of D8.6, which consists of a website and social media plan and was submitted in May, 2021. An inventory based on the Twitter audience was reported. Another inventory that had analysed the vast majority of ConcePTION followers was presented. Then the two newly launched channels, namely LinkedIn and E-mail newsletter, were introduced. The e-mail newsletter resulted in a 98.5% audience growth from WP2 webinar, increase from 253 to 560 subscribers in Q1 2022, open count of 6,253 times, and link click count of 1,736. WP6 recounted the visibility of the communication activities from April, 2021 to April, 2022, as well as the plans for a webinar series and outreach activity.

The consortium was also reminded to let the communication activities team know whenever they had publications coming, they were to present in a conference or to be interviewed by local/national media. This way the team will be able to do publicity for them.

Q&A: Each of the above presentations was followed by a short but interactive and engaging Q&A session.

GAM – Day 2

The following was presented and discussed during the second day of the GAM:

Day 2 Agenda – ConcePTION GAM (April 7, 15:00-17:00 CET)

Agenda Thursday, April 7	Time (CET)
Welcome and introduction	15:00 – 15:05 (5 min)
Keynote address PRGLAC	15:05 – 15:30 (25 min)
Presentations on key topics (10 min + 5 min Q&A for each WP) WP3: Key results and achievements from year 3 WP4: Norwegian demonstration lactation study and analytical work WP7: Data quality framework & pregnancy algorithm	15:30 – 16:15 (45 minutes)
The importance of ConcePTION for IHI, and general feedback	16:15 – 16:25 (10 min)
Feedback from the Scientific Advisory Board	16:25 – 16:40 (15 min)
Q&A + Closing	16:40 – 17:00 (20 min)

Figure 4. Agenda for day 2 of the GAM

Keynote address: PRGLAC Task Force on Research Specific to Pregnant and Lactating Women

The presentation initiated with a description of the PRGLAC Task Force. Then the central theme of PRGLAC discussions, a list of recommendations, and PRGLAC implementation plans were unfolded, respectively. WPs' themes in common with the PRGLAC recommendations were mentioned. These were followed by an action strategy in the implementation plans.

Work Package 3 – Key results and achievements from year 3

WP3 was started with one of the first pillars of the tools currently being developed to assess the drug concentration in milk and possibly for the children. Then the collaborative work of the in vitro staff from UNIBO for a final comparison between human cell line and primary human mammary epithelial cells was presented. Furthermore, it was informed that this year the group has started working with in vitro (mini)pig mammary epithelial cells. The characterization of HMECs primary line was provided. Also, the porcine mammary epithelial cells from minipig were discussed. As the following pillar tool, the in vivo achievements of year 3 were listed. The presenter reported a pilot in vivo experiment in lactating minipig sows, an example of this study's calendar, and some of its key results. WP3 was concluded with the third pillar tool used for the evaluation of exposure via milk of the children when the mothers are treated. For this reason, the PBPK achievements of year 3, regulatory application, and modelling in WP3 were elaborated, respectively.

Work Package 4 – Norwegian demonstration lactation study and analytical work

At the start of WP4, the proof of concept for the demonstration drugs for biobanking and lactation studies was introduced. The presenter interpreted the bioanalytical method development and validation, as well as of the matrices and validation parameters. Then a synopsis of a demonstration study on levocetirizine/cetirizine levels in human milk was provided. First, allergy in breastfeeding

women and second-generation antihistamines usage was highlighted. The numerous composing levels of the study design were explained. Later the ethics committee comments, practical issues, and recruitment strategy were mentioned. WP4 came to an end by sharing the data related to the samples shipped, aliquoted, and stored in the Uppsala biobank.

Work Package 7 – Data quality framework & pregnancy algorithm

The aim of WP7 was to discuss the data quality framework, which has been developed while working with population health care data, as well as the pregnancy algorithm that has been built to identify cohorts of pregnant women in such data. Firstly, the presenter clarified and illustrated the pregnancy script, including the following: inclusion, grouping, reconciliation, main variables, reconciliation variables, and validation example. Moreover, the current status, the results (yearly number of pregnancies and distribution of type of end), and features of the algorithm were shared. Secondly, the different levels of quality checks pipeline applied in the ConcePTION CDM model were analysed. Level 1 checks objectives along with three examples (namely values check, dates check, and missing data analysis) were described. Then Level 2 checks, its objectives, and an example of event dates before birth were detailed. Explanations of Level 3 checks and types of analyses were later provided, and the approval form process was delineated.

The importance of ConcePTION for IHI and general feedback

The presenter opened her talk by clarifying why ConcePTION is important to the Innovative Health Initiative (IHI). Then the measuring of impact through different lenses, which are mostly aligned with the IHI KPI framework, was introduced. Then the IMI publications increase year-on-year was mentioned. Next followed the field manual for resourcing IMI projects with scale and uptake blueprint, as well as the set of EU tools to help disseminate the results and to find some way of increasing the exploitation. Also, an overview of IHI as Europe's new partnership for health, along with novelties in the field were provided. The IHI's general and more specific objectives were listed. At the end, the IHI contributions to EU policies (SRIA) were communicated.

Ethics

The ethics framework was provided by first presenting ConcePTION as a learning healthcare system (LHS). The goal is to look at the key principles for the development of an ethically responsible LHS for pregnant and breastfeeding people were. The pursued empirical method and conceptual approach were mentioned. Furthermore, the ConcePTION Ecosystem was described as a LHS. The Ethics framework was concluded by a detailed commentary on its different levels.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the virtual GAM was an efficient and effective activity for sharing & learning and provided a 'touch base' moment for all the consortium members in the situation caused by the Covid-19 pandemic. The participants were actively involved during the presentations and during the breakout sessions. The presentation of the achievements of the project provided a clear overview of the progress of the project. The presentations given by the WP leaders provided more specific information/overview regarding the activities carried out by every work package.

In addition, the members of the Advisory Board attended the 1st and the 2nd day. They provided positive feedback and suggestions on how to move forward. The feedback provided by the members will be used as part of the deliverable *D8.11 Report from Advisory Board and Ethic Report*.

Feedback from the Scientific Advisory Board

Ms Elizabeth Conover, member of the Scientific Advisory Board, commented that she feels impressed by the work that members of the Consortium are doing. She, however, noted that there had not been a lot of mention of health literacy, her area of expertise. So, Ms Conover showed the

willingness to collaborate or provide input to interested individuals on related topics. Also, since she is doing clinical pharmacogenetics, Ms Conover would be happy to provide some insight into that (e.g., ethical issues, practical issues). **MD Lynne Yao** from FDA shared her excitement for all of the work that the IMI ConcePTION has done so far. She stated that hopefully the FDA will help to contribute in the future by collaborating and moving forward with some of the ConcePTION's work to the extent that these efforts can be made globally beneficial and useful. **Dr Jan Piasecki** from JUMC also noted how the presentations had quite impressed him. He was particularly interested in the ethical framework. Furthermore, Dr Piasecki would be curious to look into the online informed consent process in the lactation study. **Dr Niklas Norén** from UMC congratulated the consortium on all the progress they've made. He was keen to know whether there are any efforts being made to explore the aspects of the common data model, which are unique to pregnancy and lactation, in order to analyse whether they can be integrated to the OMOP CDM. Dr Norén believes this is a view worth exploring in terms of sustainability and having a long-term impact. Dr Christina Chambers from UCSD mentioned how great it was to hear especially the presentation of WP1 about the consideration of confounders and how complex.

Repository for primary data

The presentation slides and the recording of the webinar can be downloaded from ConcePTION's internal project web space.